

**STRATEGIC ISSUES OF LOCAL FASHION BRAND
DEVELOPMENT****Eshmatov Sanjar Azimkulovich**

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ABSTRACT

In the context of digital transformation and changing consumer preferences, developing their own fashion brand is becoming an urgent task for companies. This task is especially important for companies seeking to maintain competitiveness in a saturated market.

The results of other studies are also analyzed within the framework of the study. The scientific literature on fashion brand development strategies follows a multifaceted approach, covering issues of digital transformation, consumer engagement, sustainable development and ecological marketing.

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The results of other studies are also analyzed within the framework of the study. The scientific literature on fashion brand development strategies follows a multifaceted approach, covering issues of digital transformation, consumer engagement, sustainable development and ecological marketing.

For example, Yoo J. emphasizes the importance of digital communications and active participation of consumers in social networks, which is especially important for brands in the luxury segment. Gómez M., Lopez C. and Molina A.'s study developed an integrated approach to audience engagement, which reveals the mechanisms for building trusting relationships and brand loyalty. At the same time, Chen R. et al. describe the characteristics of consumer engagement models focused on brand authenticity.

Research on sustainable development issues is also important. The work of Neha J. P. and Kumar N. highlights the role of environmentally friendly initiatives in building a positive image of fast fashion brands. Chen Y.[1], Huang A., Wang T. and Chen Y.'s study analyzes environmental issues and emphasizes the need to maintain a genuine environmental image.

In additional studies, Abrar M.[2], Sibtain M. M., Shabbir R., Fuxman L. et al., as well as Adamkiewicz J.[3] and co-authors, and Carter K.[5], Jayachandran S. and Murdock M. R. considered a company's sustainability reputation as an important factor in building consumer trust and loyalty. Also, in the work of Akoglu H. E. [4] and Özbek O., the qualitative and emotional experience of the brand is emphasized, and the importance of emotional connection in forming long-term relationships between the brand and the consumer is shown.

The results of other scientific works were also analyzed within the framework of the study, and the literature on fashion brand development strategies covered such areas as digital transformation, consumer engagement, sustainable development and ecological

marketing. For example, Yoo J. emphasizes the importance of digital communications and participation in social networks, which is especially relevant for luxury brands. Gómez M. and co-authors developed an integrated approach to audience engagement, showing the mechanisms for building brand loyalty. Chen R. describes the features of engagement models based on brand authenticity.

Sustainability research is also important: Neha J. P. and Kumar N. highlight the role of environmental initiatives in brand image. Chen Y. et al. emphasize the need to maintain a genuine environmental image. Additional research considers a company's sustainability reputation as a factor in increasing consumer trust and loyalty. Akoglu H. and Özbek O. show that the emotional experience of a brand is important for long-term relationships.

In general, there is a contradiction in the literature between emotional-intuitive approaches and pragmatic methods aimed at assessing environmental responsibility. The lack of objective assessment tools for greenwashing and the weak integration of digital and traditional branding indicate the need for additional research.

The research methodology is based on the synthesis of empirical data and the integration of modern theoretical models. Digital transformation is fundamentally changing the nature of communication in the fashion industry, strengthening emotional and cognitive connections between brands and consumers through social networks.

A comprehensive approach, developed on the basis of empirical research and synthesis of theoretical models, allows us to comprehensively understand the development strategies of fashion brands in a changing market environment. The literature review emphasizes not only the importance of digital communications and consumer engagement, but also the relevance of integrating the principles of sustainable development.

Theoretical research methods create a methodological basis for practical recommendations through the analysis of cognitive, affective and behavioral components, as well as modeling diversification and synergy strategies. The next section will highlight the many years of experience in the formation of the Mursak brand, showing the evolution of the business model and success factors. The founder of the brand initially gained experience through the activities of a sewing workshop and collaborated with Tashkent designers. Due to the risks associated with payment discipline, an independent brand creation strategy was chosen.

Since 2017, with the entry of the Mursak brand into the market, sales volumes have increased. Active participation in the Wildberries and Ozon platforms, an assortment of up to 60 colors, and professional photo shoots have strengthened its competitive advantage. Analytical pricing and inventory management increased repeat purchases. Local production and collaboration created an ecosystem. B2B projects, capsule collaborations, and flexible strategies ensured sustainable growth. Success in the digital era relies on the integration of marketing, diversification, and sustainability.

The main goal was to offer affordable prices, high quality, and recognizable styling, and the color palette and assortment diversity formed a loyal customer base. Each year, designer capsule collections were presented, aimed at a narrow audience. Key management decisions included optimizing logistics and the supply chain, implementing quality control, and abandoning models that were in low demand.

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